

ELIXIR Commissioned Service Report for Deliverables/Milestones

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Title	Identify and map critical components of the Training Platform that have significant impact on the roles and responsibilities of Training Coordinators and TrP members
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Abbreviations and Acronyms

TrP	Training Platform
TrC	Training Coordinator
F2F	Face to face
HoN	Head of Node
NC	Node Coordinator
TeC	Technical Coordinator
TrCG	Training Coordinators Group
FG	Focus Groups

Contents

Document info	1
Version history	1
Author List	3
Abbreviations and Acronyms	5
Executive Summary	7
Outcomes and Impacts of the deliverable	8

Executive Summary

The Milestone M3.9 “Identify and map critical components of the Training Platform that have significant impact on the roles and responsibilities of Training Coordinators and TrP members” shows all the critical components of the Training Platform (TrP) that are either related to the Training Coordinators (TrC) or the TrP members. This milestone represents an attempt to categorize them, in order to group them. The document contains links to related information in order to have a spherical view. The objective of the milestone is to help identify the roles and responsibilities of the TrCs and the activities of the TrP members. Effort has been made in order to collect all information from past ELIXIR meetings (monthly, F2F, All Hands, related workshops) and related documentation (public and private, eg. Elixir site, papers, posters, Handbooks, deliverables etc). This is an ongoing process with future meetings in order to further discuss and continue the collection of the critical components.

The related document with critical components of the Training Platform has been created. The document has been read, commented and approved from TrCs of all Nodes and also from the other WPs, related FG and other related Commission Services as seen in the linked document.

Outcomes and Impacts of the milestone

Even from the title of the M3.9 Milestone “Identify and map critical components of the Training Platform that have significant impact on the roles and responsibilities of Training Coordinators and TrP members” it is clear that those critical components will help define and formalize the roles and expectations of Training Coordinators and Training Platform member. This clarity will enhance operational efficiency and facilitate new Training Coordinators' onboarding. These WP activities have clear complementary links to ELIXIR-STEERS WP4 ‘Strengthening and equipping ELIXIR Nodes and Node staff with key skills and resources in organization, management and Training in addition to links to the People and the Node Tier.

The related document with critical components of the Training Platform is [linked](#).